

SMART – Systematic Method of Axiomatic Robustness-Testing

- Holistic Robust Design Method for the design of robust and reliable products -

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MOTIVATION:

- Structured process and combining different Robust Design Methods not available
- Chronological Classification of Taguchi in the early stages of the Product Development Process
- Integration of reliability in Robust Design

OBJECTIVE:

- Creation of a holistic Robust Design and Reliability Method with
- Adaptive entry points into the Method and
- Iterative improvement of the product

CONCLUSIONS:

SMART is based on established methods (Axiomatic Design and the Taguchi Method) and applies VDI2221 as a chronology. Hence, SMART refers to already successfully applied methods and experiences. Compared to the known and established methods, SMART goes even further by adapting and combining these methods to a holistic approach with adaptive entry possibilities. Additionally, several limitations of the Taguchi Method are improved. Another major impact is the forecast of the reliability and advice of a possible test strategy.

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